

Artistic Research in the Post-Colonial Era

Lin Wei-Ya, Arno Böhler, Susanne Valerie Granzer, Johannes Kretz

Abstract. This panel is structured by two performance lectures (20 minutes each) presenting two artistic research projects, followed by a dialogue between the panelists. The performance lectures introduce baseCollective, a residency program for Artistic Research and Arts-Based-Philosophy in South India, and creative (mis)understandings, a project about methodologies of inspiration with indigenous people in Taiwan. The panel will discuss implications on the definition of artistic research (AR) when dealing with diverse cultural contexts.

Over the last 20 years, Böhler and Granzer have developed the format of *Philosophy On Stage*, which has become an internationally recognized role model for AR and arts-based philosophy. The method of staging philosophical problems in transdisciplinary field-performances is their basic approach of an art-laboratory during a 3-month residency-program in Tamil Nadu. Contemporary Topics are reflected from at least two sides: a globalized contemporary perspective and the perspective of Indian philosophical traditions.

The AR project creative (mis)understandings by Kretz and Lin aims to develop transcultural approaches of inspiration (regarded as mutually appreciated intentional and reciprocal artistic influence based on solidarity) by combining approaches from contemporary music composition with engaged ethnomusicology/activist research.

In Nietzschean terms all the panelists could be named artist-philosophers or philosopher-artists with a hybrid background as musicians and performers, as well as theoreticians and philosophers. Established with a theoretical and a practical background—including embodied (tacit) knowledge—the diversity of the panelists' competences will enable a discussion of current political and social movements from a post-colonial perspective by addressing the ethical differences between intercultural appropriation (the logic of the gift, Derrida), and intercultural misappropriation (the logic of power, Foucault). The dialogue will focus on ethics, aesthetics, and politics questioning the role of artistic practices in the era of globalization (Spivak): how do philosophy or art change when leaving the ivory tower by moving into public space aiming for social relevance? How can artistic practice and ethnomusicological research join forces in a collaborative setting of arts-based activist research? Which methods emerge from diversity sensitive production and dissemination formats? How does activist research and activist art production differ from research about communities?

Arno Boehler teaches at the University of Vienna, Department of Philosophy (faculty member) and at the University of Applied Arts Vienna. He is founder of the philosophy performance festival *Philosophy On Stage* and head of the residency program for arts-based philosophy and artistic research in South-India (baseCollective). Together with Susanne Valerie Granzer he has developed new cross-disciplinary strategies between philosophy and the arts to give back to philosophy its materiality, corporeality, sensibility, and vulnerability. In this context, Boehler was principal investigator of three research projects funded by the Austrian Science Funds (FWF): “Artist-Philosophers. Philosophy as Arts-Based Research” (AR

275-G21); “Generating Bodies” (TRP12-G21) and “Materiality and Temporality of Performative Speech-Acts” (P17600-G06). He has been a visiting research fellow at the University of Bangalore, the University of Heidelberg, New York University, University of Princeton and a visiting professor at the University of Applied Arts Vienna, the University of Arts Bremen (HdK Bremen), the University of Music and Performing Art Vienna, the University of Vienna and Berlin University of the Arts (UdK Berlin).

Further information: <http://homepage.univie.ac.at/arno.boehler/php/>

Susanne Valerie Granzer is a professional actress and emeritus professor at the renowned Max Reinhardt Seminar within the University of Music and Performing Arts, Vienna. Parallel to her career in acting, she was awarded a Ph.D. in philosophy by the University of Vienna in 1995. Her research focuses on the actor on stage, artistic research, and performance philosophy. She often collaborates on lecture performances alongside Viennese philosopher Arno Boehler, with whom she directs the baseCollective residency program for arts-based philosophy and artistic research in South India. Together they also founded the Viennese art factory GRENZ_film, and are the driving force behind, and main curators of, the international festival series, Philosophy on Stage. One of her books *Schauspieler außer sich. Exponiertheit und performative Kunst* (transcript 2011, 2nd edition 2014) was published in English by Palgrave Macmillan in 2016: *Actors and the Art of Performance. Under Exposure* (<http://www.palgrave.com/la/book/9781137596338>) Latest publication: “Philosophy On Stage” (Passagen Verlag: Vienna, 2018) and *Performance Philosophy Journal*, Vol. 3, No. 2 and No 3 (2017)

Website: <https://www.susannegranger.at/>

Johannes Kretz, a composer, electronics performer and artistic researcher, is head of the Artistic Research Center of mdw – University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna and co-project leader of the PEEK project creative (mis)understandings. Selected Scholarships and Awards: Austrian Federal Grant (1997), Stiftung Delz (CH, 2001), Theodor Körner Prize (2004). Commissions of work & performances: at/with National Theater Hall, Taipei, Wien modern festival, Festival Ars Electronica, Konzerthaus Wien, Eclat festival Stuttgart, Klangforum Wien, Ensemble On Line, Vienna Flautists, quartett22, Internationale Lemgoer Orgeltage, Haller Bachtage, Triton Trombone Quartett, Wiener Kammerchor. Performances in Austria, Germany, Poland, France, Czechia, Hungary, Turkey, Latvia, Lithuania, Argentina, Mexico, Canada, USA, Japan, South Korea, Taiwan, China, Uzbekistan, Iran, India.

Lin Wei-Ya, an ethnomusicologist and a violist, co-leads the PEEK-project in artistic research, creative (mis)understandings (2018-2021), at the University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna (mdw). She is also Senior Artistic Researcher and adjunct lecturer at mdw and the University of Vienna. She is initiator and curator of aNOther festival Vienna since 2010; she has led the summer camp iKultLab in arts since 2014; and since 2013 she has been involved in planning and developing projects based on scholarly research results, which are implemented by artistic inventions and activist and socio-political approaches. In 2006 she completed her M.A. in viola performance with distinction at mdw, followed by the

postgraduate curriculum in chamber music in 2007. In 2015 she received her PhD in Ethnomusicology from the same university for the thesis Music in the Life of the Tao (Taiwanese indigenous ethnic group): Tradition and Innovation, graduating with distinction.

Website: <https://www.mdw.ac.at/ike/?PageId=3652>

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